

THE DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF AN EXPLOSION RESISTANT LUGGAGE CONTAINER

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ABSTRACT: In December of 1988, Pan Am flight 103 was subjected to a catastrophic terrorist bombing resulting from an improvised explosive device hidden in the checked luggage. Immediately afterwards, the technical community embarked on several studies on how to preclude another such event. It wasn't until late 2001 that the first hardened unit load device (HULD) was successfully certified with FAA/TSA full blast and airworthy approval. This paper describes the development and design activity performed by Telair International (formally Century Aero Products) and DuPont that culminated with a practical solution offered to the airlines that could prevent another similar tragedy.

KEYWORDS: Blast tolerant membranes, aramid fabrics, Hardened Unit Load Device (HULD), explosives, aircraft survivability

INTRODUCTION

The mitigation of the effects of an unwanted bomb blast in the cargo compartment of an aircraft at high altitude is a challenge, but is an extraordinary challenge when one factors in the constraints of minimal weight and cost, while introducing no extraordinary handling requirements. The approach taken by this team was to modify existing ULD's by substituting aramid fabric reinforced composite panels for what were either thin aluminum or polycarbonate panels. The objective was to prevent the breaching of the fuselage by explosive shock or fragments, limit the damage to the airframe and preclude an onboard fire following the blast. Initial testing began the early 1990's with 4.0' x 4.0' wide panels, constructed from various fabrics, ply count and lamination detail mounted in a rigid, open top, cubic frame. A bare Detasheet®-C explosive charge was detonated at the center of the volume and the candidate panels were recovered and inspected for damage. A blast scaled study was performed where the deflection history of these panels was observed with high-speed photography.

Once we discovered the extent of a membrane strength necessary to withstand the direct blast from a surrogate explosive device, we had to determine the means of connecting the membranes to the frame. Here, two levels of analytic modeling were applied. Simple scaled distance methodology of blast waves and more detailed Dyna3D calculations allowed for estimates of the normal stresses at the coupling locations of the frame. Candidate laminate coupons were tested to verify the capacity of the composite material for this type of loading. Fastener and connection details were designed to accommodate these loads. A novel end fixture technique was invented which transferred the large membrane stresses to the frame without membrane rupture or separation. The Dyna3D calculations also provided some initial ranges of HULD panel lateral

deflections that would later prove to be critical for limiting any potential structural damage imparted to the aircraft.

While the initial calculations were in process, a systematic experimental effort was initiated where full scale HULDs were tested with ever-increasing bomb loads, varying bomb placements, and varying extents of luggage fill. Many attempts for containment were unsuccessful. A series of iterative live blast tests progressed by redesigning whatever was identified as the next weakest link. It was observed that the original aluminum extrusion frame was not adequate, the bolt patterns were marginal or the membranes breached by blast or projectile. We eventually moved in a direction, which allowed the blast to deform the shape of the box into that of a sphere. We concluded that the membranes need to deform but not separate from one another at the joints. This required the controlled deformation of the frame. In addition, a practical blast resistant door had to be developed and was eventually demonstrated in full scale blast testing.

It wasn't until 1995 that the FAA eventually defined the requirements for the HULD and began the certification testing at the Army Test Center at Aberdeen. We continued the iterative learning process as one after another design fell short of meeting all of the expectations. Tests included "shock holing", projectile impact, full-scale tests in surrogate airframes and full-scale tests in actual airframes. On August 14, 2001 we finally got it right and successfully passed the FAA blast test portion of the certification process.

This paper will now review in greater detail this exciting journey leading to a satisfactory solution. Conclusions will include what we believe is required for a reasonably lightweight container that addresses all of the current FAA and customer specifications.

INITIAL DESIGN APPROACHES

In November 1990, Congress enacted public law 101-604, much in response to the terrorist bombing of Pan Am flight 103 over Lockerbie Scotland. While this was not the first such event, it brought the issue of hardening aircraft for domestic air travel to the research, development and manufacturing community. Gatto [1] describes one of the first studies responding to this legislation. In this report, a summary of the approaches recommended by the Presidential Commission is presented. One specific recommendation relates to the hardening of existing ULDs (Unit Load Devices) as a means to safely manage the explosion that could occur if an uncased (minimal threat from metallic fragmentation) explosive charge of small size were to escape detection during luggage screening. Several approaches were identified and some were carried through to evaluation, but what we will now describe is the specific approach selected by the team formed between Telair International and DuPont (with support from Sandia National Labs, Lawrence Livermore National Labs and Maxwell Labs (S-Cubed)).

In general the approach was to modify existing, flight-worthy ULDs in ways that would not lose the original capabilities. Until 1995 when the FAA issued the draft specification (ISO 6517 and draft appendix A) for HULD (hardened unit load devices), it was never certain as to what the system constraints or design requirements would be. Initially, we worked closely with the FAA to understand what was anticipated and assumed that existing system constraints would be continued with some relaxation for modest increase in weight and price. Fig. 1 is a photograph of a typical LD-3 ULD. It weighs in the neighborhood of 80 Kg, has internal volume of 4.3 cubic meters, and has nominal dimensions of 2.0 x 1.5 x 1.6 (LxWxH) meters. A lightweight aluminum frame is constructed from high-strength extrusions that incorporate bolted and riveted connections and clamping hardware that mate to thin (1.5 mm) aluminum or polycarbonate panels (membranes). In addition to the inherent corner bracing of the frame, the membranes provide in-

plane shear stability for bracing of the structure. An easy access door panel can be opened and closed quickly while ensuring the containment of luggage during normal flight conditions. The floor of the container is clamped to the cargo bay around the perimeter of the aluminum base plate to restrain the container and its contents during all normal flight conditions.

Figure 1. Typical LD-3 ULD

The obvious candidate to meet the as-of-yet-undefined bomb containment requirement was to replace the existing panels of aluminum with those of higher membrane capacity. Not knowing the agreed upon threat specification, we initially assumed that the explosive source would be of the order of the Lockerbie bomb (14 oz. Semtex [Aviation Week and Space Technology, Dec. 2 1991]). For obvious security reasons, further description of the details of the design requirements related to the type and amount of explosive that the HULD is intended to accommodate will not be provided. There are many different grades of Semtex and certainly the energetic level of the constituents influences the magnitude of the internal stresses developed along with other unknown variables associated with bomb positioning, shape and luggage fill. Nonetheless, in order to get started, we needed to get an estimate of what was required of panel membranes to sustain localized blast loading from the bomb itself, any fragmentation originating from the acceleration of the luggage surrounding it and any later effects associated with gas build-up or burning of the luggage and its contents.

RIGID FRAME EVALUATION

Our initial evaluation of the blast tolerance of various fabric reinforced membranes involved the building of a rigid, re-usable steel frame with candidate panels clamped (more accurately, pinned) along their four edges. Figures 2a,b present the 0.122 m cubic frame with panels attached, with an open top and an explosive charge positioned at the center. The explosive charge was a spherical mass formed from DuPont's Detasheet®-C (62% PETN, 6% NC) plastic explosive. Hopkinson scaling (cube root scaling [2]) was used to estimate the reflected peak overpressure

and impulse of a free field blast wave at the position of the panel center. This approach ignores geometric effects related to reflections from the structure and ground plane, details of the charge geometry, the later build-up of gas pressure in a partially vented container and certainly the influence of the luggage on the blast wave prior to engaging the container walls. With all the uncertainty noted, we estimated peak reflected overpressures of the order of 2 Mpa with the size bomb selected. Assuming further that this pressure was uniformly distributed over the entire exposed surface and that the membrane reactions at the clamp boundary were also uniform, we estimated 700 KN/m. Due to the symmetry involved, it was possible to test four different panels with one detonation, each panel exposed to the same pressure and impulse with similar boundary conditions. Four separate tests with sixteen different panel constructions were performed. Parameters included variable fabric styles, ply count from one to four, resin matrix, and percent resin content.

Figure 2 a,b,c,d Rigid frame tests of candidate membrane materials

Figure 2c identifies the typical appearance of the panel debris following one test. Unfortunately, failures predominated near the clamp edges with evidence of transverse shear cuts, localized tensile ruptures and tensile failure associated with bolt hole tear-out. We were particularly interested in whether there was evidence of ruptures originating from the center of the panel, implying that the membrane capacity under localized blast loading had been exceeded. We were able to verify that a three-ply fabric construction with an ionic copolymer film matrix appeared adequate to accommodate the localized blast loading (also called shock holing) developed in this conservative test configuration. It was also apparent that the rigid connections would result in failures in the membranes near the frame connections.

Along with the experiments above, DuPont pursued a more detailed study [3] of the response of several fabric-based laminates to similar explosive blast loading. Applying the Hopkinson scaling directly, we constructed a reduced scale reproduction of the rigid frame test but used a high speed framing camera to record the initial deflection history of the center of the panels under equivalent explosive blast loads. One of the boundary conditions was adjusted to a free condition out of necessity in order to observe one edge directly. The trends identified were consistent with those of the rigid frame test, but we now had additional insight related to the extent of deflection and the response time that were unavailable from the previous tests.

ULD RETROFIT EVALUATION

In parallel with the DuPont efforts above, Telair International worked with Maxwell Labs (S-Cubed) during the period 1992-1993 to evaluate the potential of existing ULDs to sustain various internal bomb explosions. Both computational and experimental approaches were taken with actual ULD designs in current use. Once again, Detasheet®-C explosives were used in ever increasing amounts, positioned in similar fashion but with simulated luggage (cardboard boxes loosely filled with rags) surrounding the bomb placement. The ULD studied was the LD-3 with polycarbonate panels, standard aluminum extrusions and the standard “wavy joint” connections of panel to extrusions (described in greater detail in the following section). Figure 1 is what one of these containers looked like. A series of eight tests were performed in sequence with ever increasing explosive until the standard container no longer contained the event. This threshold was observed and recorded as the baseline configuration. It was observed that simulated luggage fill influenced the apparent blast severity, somehow reducing the intensity of the loading delivered to the structure. Failures were observed at connection extrusions.

Following the 1995 issuing of the FAA draft specification for HULDs, it was apparent that the bomb size originally assumed was not sufficient. In 1996, Telair International re-activated the evaluations of standard ULDs but now with a greater bomb size. PETN-TNT and C-4 (95% RDX) were now used with amounts roughly twice of what was used before. The ULD design was modified in several ways to address the more severe loading requirements. Independent ballistic screening tests, using a 58-caliber black powder rifle were used to confirm the fragmentation resistance of the several Kevlar® membrane constructions. A commercial product “BlastGard” was introduced to the inside of the roof panel in an attempt to attenuate or reduce the intensity of the blast presented to this location. Two containers used polycarbonate panels modified with the addition of three plies of Kevlar® fabric bonded directly to the outer surface. One container used a three ply Kevlar® laminate along with the BlastGard roof attenuation. In most of these instances, the container failed at connections or joints. The failures included membrane pullout from the joint and either local tensile or shear failures very close to the edge of the aluminum extrusion. Figure 3 presents an example of these types of failures of the partially modified ULD. Two more attempts were made to get the standard “wavy joint” ULD to hold together under the larger blast requirement. Instead of strengthening the membranes, the extrusions were stiffened and gussets were strengthened. This final modification failed to meet the requirement as well with significant breaching of the container envelope. This collection of only partially successful full-scale tests suggested a complete re-design of the container “system”.

Figure 3. Modified ULD before and after full scale bomb test

REDESIGN EFFORT

Taking the opportunity to reflect on the observations of the many tests performed to that date, we tried to identify the predominant shortcomings. It was apparent that as the connections were stiffened, that membrane failures were more likely and prevalent in the immediate proximity of the frame extrusions. If the membranes held against localized blast loading and fragment impact, they then failed at the connections by pulling out of the wavy joint or tearing around bolt or rivet holes. It was logical to propose that a solution could be achieved by moving the design in an opposite direction. This suggested that the container frame be more flexible and that the significant membrane loads need to be managed to preclude failure at the connections.

In order to get a better estimate of the magnitude of these membrane stresses and the quantifiable extent of lateral deflections we asked for, and received analytic (modeling) assistance from both Lawrence Livermore Labs and Sandia National Labs. Livermore performed Dyna3D simulations of the LD-3 (standard ULD) with both standard membranes (aluminum and polycarbonate) and the stronger Kevlar® fabrics. The mechanical response of the fabric is quite complex and difficult to define a good constitutive relation but a simplified form was contrived and applied. The focus was on determining what level of out-of-plane deflections that the roof panel would exhibit while containing the full size explosive charge. Various stiffening concepts were evaluated including honeycomb cores, stiffer extrusions and the use of bracing stiffeners. Computational predictions of the Kevlar® panels of the order of 25 cm were consistent with the high-speed camera observations from some of the previous tests. The desire was to preclude any interaction of the roof of the LD-3 with the critical floor beams of the passenger cabin above, but we realized that making the container too stiff would likely result in breaching of the container near the connections. So, we had to identify a system design, which would allow for the maximum deflections just below what would result in structural damage to the aircraft structure. The Dyna-3D analysis also gave us a rough estimate of the magnitude of the membrane loads at the connection edges and joints.

At the same time, Howard Walther (Sandia Labs) applied conventional blast resistant structural analyses to estimate bolt sizing and spacing requirements. For the full size explosive charge and the specified geometry of the LD-3 tensile loads of the order of 9 KN/cm were estimated. The nominal load capacity of three plies of the Kevlar® fabric is 10 KN/cm, so the membrane itself was not likely a limiting factor. Restraining the membrane against this magnitude of load was apparently beyond the capacity of the wavy joint aluminum extrusion, thereby requiring some significant re-design.

We took this opportunity to evaluate the otherwise adequate Kevlar® laminate membrane against additional requirements. The membrane must also preclude perforation of flying debris from luggage surrounding the bomb. The US Government had studied the nature of debris launched from potential terrorist bombs surrounded by actual luggage. The current design requirements for the HULD include a surrogate projectile, which must be contained. This projectile can be either made of steel or lead, with a mass of 37 grams and velocity of 277 m/s. Here, DuPont has considerable experience with designing ballistic fabrics and blankets to arrest fragmentation. Unfortunately, the majority of our empirical ballistic database involves steel fragmentation with relatively sharp edges, lower masses and higher velocities. We had to extrapolate downwards with velocity to address the HULD requirement and estimated a conservative number of plies required. The nature of the projectiles emanating from random luggage must similarly be quite random, but fortunately, the conservative estimate could be relaxed due to the subsequent

experimental evaluation with the required projectile at the required velocity. Given, perhaps the smooth hemispherical nose geometry, only three plies were necessary to arrest the projectiles during the tests. Therefore, the panels were not limited by this fragmentation requirement but instead deflection, shock-holing or membrane capacity.

An extensive effort of mechanically testing various joint concepts, frame extrusions and membrane constructions was performed in order for us to select the right properties of our next substantially different HULD design. Over a period of three years, some 100 mechanical coupons, joint sections, door latch hooks and structural elements were tested to failure. Table 1 presents a summary of the type and extent of testing that was directed at carrying the loads predicted by the computational studies noted earlier. Lap shear connections and bolt cutout capacity were evaluated enough to allow the specification of minimum membrane construction, bolt sizing and spacing, and the generic connection configuration. The lightweight aluminum extrusions limit how readily the substantial membrane loads can be accommodated. Previous observations around overly stiff frame structures and the consequence of lower ballistic capacity required that we consider something different in order to restrain the substantial membrane loads that develop during the internal blast containment.

Tensile Testing Evaluation of HULD Connection Using 1.0" Width Specimens							
Material tested was Kevlar 29 fabric / Thermoplastic Matrix							
Test Specimen Number	Units (lb - force) (Newtons)	Lbs per per 1" width per ply	Normalized Lbs / End (Ult Load/end)	Normalized Lbs / end adj. for bolt hole (0.025" Diameter)	Normalized Lbs per in ply (using 21 ends)	Test Data Group	Description of Failure Modes In Each Group
1 to 8	Std Deviation	118	5.6	7.7	162.0	1	Kevlar net section or distortion failures
	Ave. (lbf)	1310	62.8	82.7	1736.0		
	Ave. (Newtons)	5827.2	279.3	367.9	7722.1		
9 to 27	Std Deviation	192	9.6	12.9	271.0	2	Kevlar failure near edge strip or connection failure
	Ave. (lbf)	1144	54.1	70.9	1488.0		
	Ave. (Newtons)	5088.8	240.6	315.4	6619.0		
28 to 30	Std Deviation	70	5.7	8.5	179.0	3	Kevlar shear out or connection failures
	Ave. (lbf)	990	46.6	61	1281.0		
	Ave. (Newtons)	4403.7	207.3	271.3	5698.2		
31 <i>(single coupon was tested)</i>	Ave. (lbf)	1906.2	91.8	NA	1906.2	4	Kevlar net section failure <i>(Specimen tested without bolts)</i>
	Ave. (Newtons)	8479.1	408.5	NA	8479.1		
	Du Pont Specification	2000.0	95.2	NA	NA	NA	NA

Table 1. Summary of mechanical evaluation of connections and joint capacities

FINAL HULD JOINT CONFIGURATION

The fundamental premise of how to accommodate the blast loads through membrane stresses at the edges and connections of the container was to not rely upon the frame extrusions to restrain the membranes. Instead, we chose to allow the lightweight, relatively compliant aluminum extrusions to flex along with the entire container as it deforms from its original orthorhombic

shape to one that approaches more of a sphere. The membrane loads are transferred from one membrane to neighboring ones, somewhat independent of the frame. The hope was to accommodate the internal blast pressures much like a balloon. An adequate balloon membrane would develop elastic or inelastic stresses as the volume expands, but not rupture under the most severe conditions. Flexural stresses could develop at the connections, but these were minimized due to the high rotational compliance of the connections. Figure 4 presents a comparison between the initial rigid frame connections, the original wavy joint used on the standard ULD and the redesigned joint now proposed for the hardened ULD. The important design aspect of the HULD joint lies with the use of continuous wrapping of the fabric reinforced laminate over mounting straps or bars that are connected directly to mating edges of neighboring panels with the same type of edge build-up. The two connected edges are also attached to the frame extrusions through common through bolts, but during blast containment, the connection to the frame is weaker than the direct coupling of the membranes. A controlled separation of the membranes from the frame seems desirable in order to allow for maximum stretching of the membranes and ultimately minimal weight for the entire structure. The contrasting requirement for limiting the potential for airframe structural damage however suggests that the frame must not entirely separate but restrain the balloon from radial deflections beyond the order of 25 cm.

Figure 4. Comparison of the membrane to frame joints on the initial rigid test frame, original ULD and final hardened design (generalized crosssections).

With the new configuration defined, the extrusion dies for the aluminum extrusions were acquired, prototype panel membranes, mounting strips and other attachment hardware were manufactured and evaluated for structural capacity. The next step was to verify that the hardened design concept met our expectations. We started this last stage of design iteration with a full-scale blast test (reduced explosive mass) with a 75% real (unclaimed baggage provided by the FAA) luggage fill. The container was not restrained as in an actual aircraft cargo bay, but simply rested on a concrete slab. The blast containment test conducted at Sandia Labs on May 1999 was successful with the container effectively containing the blast and fragmentation but due to no restraint actually launched the entire container approximately 40 cm, vertically. Late stage gas venting was allowed by the initial vent surface designed into the frame corners and openings around the flexible door. No detrimental blast effects were apparent outside of the container.

With this initial confirmation, we then submitted samples to the FAA for its independent evaluation. One series of these tests involved evaluating the membranes with “shock-holing”

tests that rigidly mount 122 x 122 cm membranes positioned close to the surrogate explosive source. Upon detonation, the blast front that is transferred through the luggage fill presents the panel material with the challenge to resist local membrane tensile rupture. Regardless of the occasional pull-out of the panels from the frame, all of the panels tested (with ply counts ranging from 3 to 8 layers) successfully met the requirement without showing evidence of panel rupture. Independent fragmentation tests were subsequently performed with similar acceptable results.

The next step for the FAA certification involved the testing of the complete containment system with varying levels of airframe interaction. A total of four separate full-scale tests were performed to FAA specifications during the period 1999 to 2001 at the Army Test Center (Aberdeen Proving Ground). The first test was performed in a wood-framed fixture that partially simulated the actual cargo compartment. The containment was unsuccessful due to perforation of the outboard panel and roof by either luggage or bomb fragmentation, leading to moderate ejection of luggage, and flow of air back into the container resulting in a potential for fire inside the container. The connections between the panels held together, even with extensive frame damage and deformation. Except for these localized breaches, the remainder of the structure was able to contain the blast products and luggage debris, venting off the gas products as desired. The anticipated solution to this undesirable result was to increase the ply count of the Kevlar® fabric panels in the obvious critical locations.

The second test, now with the HULD modified with ballistic enhanced panels was similarly disappointing but for quite different reasons. In this instance, high-speed photography was useful in identifying the sequence of events leading to system rupture, ejection of luggage, and subsequent internal fire. Here, we believe that the latching hooks of the bottom of the flexible door tore the hook portion of the floor extrusion. When the door pulled away from the floor plate, an opening formed similar to a crack that propagated along the lower edges of the container. Once the opening formed, the frame structure was unable to accommodate the stresses that the membranes were intended to carry. The entire container displaced upward due to the separation from the base plate with considerable impact damage imparted to the simulated overhead floor beams. The resolution to this apparent weakness was to strengthen the hook-channel extrusions on the floor plate. In addition, some gussets in the transition region of the sloping panel were reinforced to preclude a similar tearing of the extrusions along the lower edge.

The third container (with modified door latch extrusion and hooks) came close to meeting the full requirement with the door latch connection holding throughout the containment event. Once again, the connections between panels held everywhere, the internal frame deformed in the desired fashion allowing the container to expand and absorb the blast event and for the most part, the membranes contained the blast debris and luggage. A substantial rupture in the outboard panel resulting from an apparent fragment (or gas jet) impingement allowed the ejection of luggage and flow of combustion air back into the container resulting with internal fire once again. The high-speed photography was able to confirm that some form of high-speed fragment impact and subsequent perforation was the cause of the membrane rupture which opened up in dimension following the initial perforation. The obvious solution once again was to further increase the ply count of the membrane reinforcement in this critical location.

The fourth and final full-scale test was performed in an actual B747 forward cargo compartment on 14 August 2001. This test was fully successful with the blast adequately contained. This test also served as necessary step towards meeting the FAA certification requirements. Figure 5 presents the successful HULD design before and during the containment event. Following the inspection of airframe structure, and review of outboard pressure histories, the FAA allowed the design to receive the only TSO C90c certification on the market.

Figure 5. Bomb blast certification test of HULD before and during containment

CONCLUSIONS

Current luggage containers (ULD) were evaluated for the potential to provide secondary security to aircraft in the instance of an undetected bomb explosion in the luggage compartment. It was found that the existing containers would not easily meet the projected requirements specified by the FAA. A primarily experimental effort executed over more than a decade, eventually lead to a satisfactory solution to this problem. This substantial re-design of existing lightweight containers was guided by computational modeling, quasi-static mechanical characterization and the necessary trial-and-error testing at various blast loading scales. Now that this design has received FAA certification and is being employed by specific commercial operators, the hope is that it will now be implemented on a more widespread basis to increase the safety of commercial air travel. Whether via government mandate, government subsidy or purely commercial market forces, this now-proven technology should be made available to the general flying public. Given the geo-political environment we see today, security threats similar to those that brought down Pan Am 103 in 1988 will be with us for some time.

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